

Binuclear Oxofluoro Complex of Quinquevalent Molybdenum

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VERY little work has been done on the oxofluoro complexes of Mo(V) compared to an extensive volume of work on the analogous oxochloro complexes. It is well known that paramagnetic oxochloromolybdates(V) hydrolyse as the acid concentration is decreased and ultimately dimrise to give oxo bridged diamagnetic or very weakly paramagnetic complexes. There are a few reports¹⁻³ till now on the preparation of oxo bridged Mo(V) fluoro complexes, but none of these has been adequately characterised. We have studied the magnetic susceptibility of $[\text{MoOF}_6]^{2-}$ at different HF concentrations and have isolated a binuclear complex $\text{K}_4[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{F}_6] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$.

Experimental

$\text{K}_2[\text{MoOF}_6]$ and $\text{MoO}(\text{OH})_2$ were prepared by methods reported earlier^{1,4}. Molybdenum was analysed gravimetrically as oxinate⁵, after decomposing the sample with fuming HNO_3 and H_2SO_4 . The methods of analysis of potassium and fluorine and the determination of the oxidation state of molybdenum (by oxidation with dichromate) were described earlier^{6,7}.

Magnetic susceptibility was determined by Gouy method using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as calibrant. The diamagnetic corrections were taken from standard sources⁸. The magnetic susceptibility of $\text{K}_2[\text{MoOF}_6]$ or $\text{MoO}(\text{OH})_2$ in aqueous HF was measured at 30° using polythene tubes having ebonite stopper. The molybdenum content in aliquots was determined by oxinate method [after removal of F^- and oxidation of Mo(V)]. That all molybdenum was practically present as Mo(V) was checked by the determination of Mo(V) in aliquots by oxidation with dichromate.

Infrared spectra in the range of 4000-650 cm^{-1} were recorded using a Perkin Elmer spectrophotometer No. 257. Electronic spectra were recorded with Carl Zeiss DMR-21 and Carl Zeiss, Jena VSU2-P spectrophotometers.

Preparation of $\text{K}_4[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{F}_6] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Potassium fluoride (14.0 g; 0.24 mole) dissolved in 2% HF was added to a concentrated solution of $\text{MoO}(\text{OH})_2$ (1.0 g; 0.006 mole) in 2% HF. The brown red micro crystalline substance was separated by filtration and dried by pressing between filter papers and then keeping in a desiccator over H_2SO_4 and NaOH. The yield was 0.5 g (29%). (Anal. Found :

Mo, 33.6; F, 20.0; K, 27.7. Calcd. for $\text{K}_4[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{F}_6] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$; Mo, 34.1; F, 20.3; K, 27.8%). The same compound was also obtained by mixing together aqueous solutions of $\text{K}_2[\text{MoOF}_6]$ (0.3 g) and KF (2.4 g).

Results and Discussion

The magnetic susceptibility of $\text{K}_2[\text{MoOF}_6]$ in HF medium has been measured as a function of the acid concentration. Because of the limited solubility of $\text{K}_2[\text{MoOF}_6]$ in dilute HF we preferred to use $\text{MoO}(\text{OH})_2$. It is known¹ that $\text{MoO}(\text{OH})_2$ dissolves in 40% HF from which green crystalline salts $\text{M}_2[\text{MoOF}_6]$ can be isolated by the addition of alkali metal fluorides. In a few representative cases it was checked that equimolecular solutions of $\text{K}_2[\text{MoOF}_6]$ and of $\text{MoO}(\text{OH})_2$ in HF medium of identical concentration registered almost the same magnetic susceptibility.

The molar magnetic susceptibility of a solution of $\text{MoO}(\text{OH})_2$ or $\text{K}_2[\text{MoOF}_6]$ in 40% HF was found to be about 1310×10^{-6} cgs units and the magnetic moment was 1.79 B.M. As the acid concentration was lowered the solutions turned from light green to brownish red and the susceptibility decreased. Ultimately, at an acid concentration of about 3%, the solution was diamagnetic. This behaviour of $[\text{MoOF}_6]^{2-}$ is very similar⁹ to that of $[\text{MoOCl}_6]^{2-}$. The susceptibility of solutions of $\text{MoO}(\text{OH})_2$ in dilute HF did not change on standing for half an hour.

$\text{K}_4[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{F}_6] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is soluble in water from which it can be recrystallised. It loses the two molecules of water slowly at 140°. The molecular conductance of $1 \times 10^{-3} M$ aqueous solution (650 $\text{ohm}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^2$) at 30° indicates some dissociation of the anion. The complex is very weakly paramagnetic (μ_{eff} is 0.20 B.M. at 30°). IR spectra give bands due to $\nu(\text{OH})$ and $\delta(\text{H}_2\text{O})$ at about 3500 and 1650 cm^{-1} . The terminal $\nu(\text{Mo}=\text{O})$ modes appear at 950 vs, 925 vs and 905 m, while two bridging MoO_2Mo modes occur at 845 vs and 740 vs which agree with the presence of a bent MoO_2Mo bridge with the $\text{Mo}=\text{O}$ groups on the same side of the bridge (i.e., *cis*)¹⁰.

Like other complexes containing $\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_7^{2+}$ the electronic spectra of $\text{K}_4[\text{Mo}_2\text{O}_4\text{F}_6] \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ do not display the low energy transitions which are characteristics of monomeric MoO_4^{2-} complexes¹⁰. The reflectance or the Nujol mull spectra gave two bands at about 20,000 and 23,000 cm^{-1} .

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**Polymeric Metal Complexes of
5,5'-(*p*-phenylenebisazo)-di-quinolin-8-ol**

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THIS communication is in continuation of the previous work on metallated complexes of 5,5'-(benzidinebisazo)-8-hydroxyquinoline¹, and is a part of work on polymeric metal complexes being carried out in our laboratories¹⁻⁶. The synthesis and characterization of the insoluble pigments derived from 5,5'-(*p*-phenylenebisazo)-di-quinolin-8-ol (abbr. PDQO) are now being reported.

Experimental

The synthesis of 5,5'-(*p*-phenylenebisazo)-di-quinolin-8-ol was carried out by tetraazotizing 0.1 mol (10.8 g) of *p*-phenylenediamine and coupling the tetraazonium salt with 0.2 mol (29.0 g) of 8-quinolinol in pyridine medium as reported earlier⁷.

Mixtures of 0.01 mol metal acetate hydrate [ammonium iron(II) sulphate in the case of Fe(II)] and 0.01 mol the above bisazo dye (4.20 g) were refluxed in DMSO for 6 hr to obtain the metallated complexes, which were filtered, washed with hot DMSO and dried as usual. The complexes were amorphous dark brown solids, insoluble in water and in the usual organic solvents.

The estimation of C, H, N and the metal, as well as spectral and thermal studies were done as described in an earlier communication¹.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data (Table 1) reveal a metal to ligand ratio of 1 : 1 as expected for a chain polymer, and the coordination of 2 H₂O per metal ion is inferred⁸. The ir spectra of the complexes of PDQO (Table 2) resemble closely those of the previously reported complexes of 5,5'-(benzidinebisazo)-8-hydroxyquinoline^{1,8}.

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TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF POLYMERIC PIGMENTS OF PDQO

Empirical formula	Analysis % Found (Calcd.)			
	C	H	N	M
MnC ₂₄ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₂ ·2H ₂ O	56.39 (56.58)	3.63 (3.53)	16.15 (16.50)	10.62 (10.82)
FeC ₂₄ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₂ ·2H ₂ O	56.27 (56.48)	3.69 (3.52)	16.42 (16.49)	10.71 (10.96)
ZnC ₂₄ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₂ ·2H ₂ O	55.19 (55.48)	3.56 (3.48)	16.11 (16.18)	12.40 (12.52)
CdC ₂₄ H ₁₄ N ₆ O ₂ ·2H ₂ O	50.45 (50.88)	3.27 (3.18)	14.64 (14.84)	19.55 (19.89)

TABLE 2—ASSIGNMENT OF IR BANDS (cm⁻¹)

PDQO	Mn(II)	Fe(II)	Zn(II)	Cd(II)	Assignment
—	3400- 3850	3400- 3850	3400- 3850	3400- 3360	^ν OH(H ₂ O)
3380- 3120	—	—	—	—	^ν OH
—	1640	1640	1630	1630	^δ OH(H ₂ O)
1600	1590	1590	1595	1595	^ν C=N
1440	—	—	—	—	^δ OH
1180	1180	1180	1180	1180	^ν C-O(O-O-M)
780	780	780	780	780	^ν M-OH ₂
625	625	625	625	625	^ν M-O
460	460	460	460	460	^ν M-N

The electronic spectrum of the bisazo dye exhibits a band at 500 nm whose high intensity and wavelength suggest a $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition attributed to the extensive conjugation resulting in lowering of the π^* orbital energy⁹. The *d-d* transition bands appear as weak shoulders on the intraligand band. The position and assignment of these bands are given in Table 3. Octahedral geometry around the

TABLE 3—ELECTRONIC SPECTRA OF Mn(II) AND Fe(II) PIGMENTS

Metal	Band (nm)	Assignment	Geometry
Mn(II)	580	⁶ A _{1g} → ⁴ T _{1g} (G)	Octahedral
	490	→ ⁴ T _{2g} (G)	
	440	→ ⁴ A _{1g} (G)	
	380	→ ⁶ E _g (G)	
	350	→ ⁴ T _{2g} (D)	
	330	→ ⁶ E _g (D)	
Fe(II)	720	⁶ B _{1g} → ⁶ B _{1g}	Octahedral

central metal is assigned¹⁰, which is in accordance with that previously reported for Co(II), Ni(II) and Cu(II) complexes⁹. In Fe(II) complex of lower symmetry, the E_g and T_{2g} states further split into A_{1g}, B_{1g} and B_{2g}, E_g.

Doubling of band is anticipated. It is assumed that the ground state is B_{2g} for these complexes, then ⁶B_{2g} → ⁶B_{1g} is 10D_q¹¹.

The modes of decomposition of these pigments resemble those of the previously reported complexes^{1,8}. The chelates begin to lose weight at an accelerated rate between 300-380° (Table 4). The